

Dataset of Youtube & TikTok Videos

YouTube Channel	YouTube Link	TikTok Account	TikTok Link
@KiaEspana	https://youtube.com/shorts/emnaCiVO0Ek	@kiaespana	https://www.tiktok.com/@kiaespana/video/7451578890595667232?_r=1&_t=ZN-8u1XbMUXq1m
	https://youtube.com/shorts/Mf3fHE7KtI4		https://www.tiktok.com/@kiaespana/video/7447181963070410016?_r=1&_t=ZN-8tdTiuWVF9b
	https://www.youtube.com/shorts/JDwZpW4G1y0		https://www.tiktok.com/@kiaespana/video/7449038021833280801?_r=1&_t=ZN-8u02zPIoROg
	https://youtube.com/shorts/qaPL81nnuXQ		https://www.tiktok.com/@kiaespana/video/7389187332663971105?_r=1&_t=ZN-8tzzIbmtT8A
	https://youtube.com/shorts/CwoIV7fJN6w		https://www.tiktok.com/@kiaespana/video/7381843308332551457?_t=ZN-8u02kn7Z6so&_r=1
@Samsung_Espana	https://www.youtube.com/shorts/WEnDkgN47Ys	@samsungespana	https://www.tiktok.com/@samsungespana/video/7425306201551850785?_r=1&_t=ZN-8u34eKUnfq2
	https://www.youtube.com/shorts/TtTazbXqR3U		https://www.tiktok.com/@samsungespana/video/7439500118048492832?_r=1&_t=ZN-8u385MoKAOU
	https://www.youtube.com/shorts/r9amwEGsVoM		https://www.tiktok.com/@samsungespana/video/7428723271366970657?_r=1&_t=ZN-8tdTBUUnBYHu

	https://www.youtube.com/shorts/Cqb74IcG12c		https://www.tiktok.com/@samsungespana/video/7436160379580960033?_r=1&_t=ZN-8u3Bwwxode
	https://www.youtube.com/shorts/YBTT1B90xek		https://www.tiktok.com/@samsungespana/video/7411196416493669664?_r=1&_t=ZN-8tdSgtbhleI
@IKEASpain	https://www.youtube.com/shorts/Hy6FDrzXfT4	@ikea.spain	https://www.tiktok.com/@ikea.spain/video/7449427582203874592?_r=1&_t=ZN-8tdRvbi7ObG
	https://youtube.com/shorts/FL03ONH1dos		https://www.tiktok.com/@ikea.spain/video/7424835606678703393?_r=1&_t=ZN-8tdS2U7aDeY
	https://youtube.com/shorts/imgSJnlc0oE		https://www.tiktok.com/@ikea.spain/video/7426039971078851873?_r=1&_t=ZN-8tdSO52IWNK
	https://www.youtube.com/shorts/1FfweyYB6ZU		https://www.tiktok.com/@ikea.spain/video/7450522666043182368?_r=1&_t=ZN-8u1Xxkc7Zeo
	https://www.youtube.com/shorts/4E2HuokQgyI		https://www.tiktok.com/@ikea.spain/video/7441890697696808224?_r=1&_t=ZN-8tdSWOJ6z4g